

Composite Reliability

Variable	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Product (X1)		0,881	0,914
Destination Quality	0,716		
Destination Uniqueness	0,827		
Tourist Attractions	0,886		
Comfort	0,853		
Security	0,832		
Price (X2)		0,923	0,942
Price competitiveness	0,824		
Tour package prices	0,895		
Discounts	0,881		
Price Affordability	0,893		
Price match	0,878		
Promotion (X3)		0,930	0,948
Social Media Interaction	0,775		
Discount campaign	0,935		
Customer testimonials	0,905		
Availability of Online Information	0,885		
Promotional quality	0,920		
Place (X4)		0,883	0,915
Accessibility	0,826		
Accommodation facilities	0,814		
Availability of tourist services	0,799		
Destination attractiveness	0,850		
Destination location	0,839		
Process (X5)		0,939	0,805
Quality of training	0,879		
Availability of Information	0,908		
Destination cleanliness	0,905		
Tourist experience Service	0,889		
People (X6)		0,928	0,776
Tour guide competency	0,817		
Credibility of the tour guide	0,905		
Communication Quality	0,916		
Responsive tour guide service	0,887		
Tour guide interaction with tourists	0,877		
Physical of Eviden (X7)		0,915	0,748
Physical Conditions of the Destination Environment	0,783		
Use of Technology	0,884		
Destination design	0,854		
Tourist Information Supervision	0,891		
Packaging (X8)		0,905	0,725
Selection of destination images	0,834		
Branding consistency	0,804		
Informative tour package packaging	0,901		
Availability of tour packages	0,861		
Quality of destination facilities	0,855		
Positioning (X9)		0,933	0,789
Destination image	0,884		
Brand identity	0,883		
Tourist segmentation	0,883		
Uniqueness of attraction	0,897		
Reputation	0,895		

Variable	Loading	Cronbach's Alpha	Composite Reliability
Satisfaction (Y1)		0,905	0,779
Product Quality	0,851		
Service quality	0,896		
Ease of access	0,910		
accessibility			
Tourist experience	0,872		
Sustainable (Y2)		0,879	0,773
Intention to return to the destination	0,884		
Recommend destinations	0,856		
Tourist trust	0,844		
Tourist satisfaction	0,841		